

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D4.6 Research design: Governmental responses - update M26

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Authors	Ioannis Bagkazounis, KEMEA Ioannis Konstantopoulos, KEMEA Anna Tsekoura, KEMEA Effrosyni Dima, KEMEA
Contributors	FS, SAPIENZA, SINUS, SU, SYNNO, TRI, UCSC, URJC, UANTWERPEN, UGOT, MDA
Reviewers	Sergei Shubin, SU Diana Beljaard, SU Vanessa Moser, SYNNO Viktoria Adler, SYNNO Diotima Bertel, SYNNO

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1.0	31.12.2022	Final Deliverable ready for submission

Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project aims to assess the government, public health, community, and resident responses as well as the role of information and communication at all stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. Through analysing and evaluating the existing strategies, influential practices, measures, and tools via a multidisciplinary and intersectional approach, the project aims to develop an online portal and toolkit for stakeholders in the governmental, public health, and civil society/community domains and provide promising practices especially related to vulnerable populations.

This report is part of work package 4 on *Government responses and impact assessment*. This work package focuses on governmental structures and responses, by reviewing them on a national level among the project target countries, as well as on a regional/local level in selected research sites and case studies, performing in parallel an in-depth analysis of key dimensions of governmental response impact in the project target countries.

This deliverable reports on task 4.2 *Conduct primary empirical research on governmental responses*. The document's main objective is to specify the research questions and methods of primary data collection and analysis to be utilised in the empirical research on governmental responses and the impacts these have on the target countries and to specific vulnerable populations. Specific ethical considerations will be also presented and assessed for the empirical research to take place.

After a short introduction of the aims and the objectives of the deliverable, the methodology is outlined. This includes a description of the aims and objectives of the research, as well as its purpose. A series of research questions have been defined to guide the research. The document further specifies the sampling criteria, and target population, as well as the specific qualitative methods utilised for the study (semi-structured interviews, focus groups discussions, etc.). Finally, the document defines the timeline for research activities, the foreseen research sites and responsible partners as well as all the ethical and legal considerations that must be taken into account.

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction.....	6
2 Overview of research activities, methodological framework and timeline	6
2.1 Overview of the desktop and empirical research in WP4.....	7
3 Methodological reflections	10
4 Conclusions.....	11
References.....	12
Literature.....	12
WP4 Deliverables	13
ANNEX. Risk mitigation strategy	14

Tables

Table 1. Example of Sociodemographic criteria for WP4 sampling population.....	8
Table 2. Overview of WP4 expert interviews.....	9

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
COVID	Corona Virus Disease
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
FGD (s)	Focus Group Discussion(s)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The initial version of the research design (D4.2) provided analytical methodological guidance to the partners involved in the previous tasks and subsequent reports (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3, D4.4, D4.5) of WP4, explaining the specific steps, requirements, deadlines as well as instructions for the data collection along with the general objectives and data collection procedures that constitute the methodological framework of the research activities. This deliverable (D4.6) is an update on the guidance that is necessary for the successful completion of *D4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment - update M31* of the WP4 and, as such, it provides an overview as well as methodological reflections of the research conducted in WP4.

In the context of WP4, the following main research questions are examined:

1. What are the main milestones of the governmental responses adopted in each country during the different pandemic phases?
2. In what ways have governmental measures been implemented and adapted across communities/populations, and have they been received?
3. In what ways have governmental responses addressed specific vulnerabilities and inequalities across diverse communities/populations?
4. What was the experience of vulnerable groups in relation to governmental response?

Participants of this task are all COVINFORM consortium partners.

2 Overview of research activities, methodological framework and timeline

WP4's main objective is to review and describe governmental structures and responses on a national level among the project target countries, as well as on a regional/local level and case studies, performing in parallel an in-depth analysis of key dimensions of governmental responses in the project target countries¹. The WP consists of four tasks which are conducted in two iterations. T4.1 aimed to acquire an overview through desk-based research (D4.1, D4.5), T4.2 outlines the empirical research design (D4.2, D4.6), T4.3 focuses on the empirical research (D4.3, D4.7), and T4.4 synthesizes the results across the tasks within the WP (D4.4, D4.8). These activities are summarized in the following paragraph.

T4.1 aimed to gather and assess **governmental responses**², including a review of relevant **primary sources** (governmental policies and guidelines, official assessments and reports, etc.) and **secondary sources** discussing these governmental responses (scholarly studies, grey literature, etc.). This resulted in a baseline report with chapters per partner country, containing top-level descriptive analysis of relevant structures and responses, cross-referenced with indicators utilized in WP2 and accompanied by an index of sources. Emphasis was put on how governmental responses correspond to the COVID-

¹ Here each participant could decide on which level of governance should focus and in relation to the following research questions, based on the reality of their countries.

² Focus was put on policies and final decisions. Any reference to political debates/discussions was not listed separately, just the final outcomes of such debates.

19 infection rate since the 24th of January 2020 (D4.1), including entries from January 2020, until the end of March 2021³. Subsequently, D4.5 examined the next phase, which was identified to be from February 2021 until late May 2022.

This deliverable, part of T4.2, outlines the empirical research design which interrelates with T4.3 and subsequently generates D4.7, which will focus on the empirical research of WP4. The methodological framework of this deliverable describes the empirical research which has been conducted in the context of WP4, including ongoing research that is currently being conducted until May 2023 in each target country. In previous research which was conducted within WP4, the focus was given to '**vulnerability**'. During the research activities conducted within the project, the interpretation of the "syndemic vulnerability" approach was adopted by the consortium in relation to vulnerable groups across and within societies, a term which has constantly been redefined in comparison to pre-existing terminology of vulnerability⁴. This approach allows highlighting the differential consequences existing within regions and populations, underlining the element of intersectionality and the impact the COVID-19 pandemic had and continues to have on vulnerable populations and the way those were affected (**physically, economically, socially, and mentally**) not only by COVID-19 but mostly from the **governmental response and reaction** to it. In addition, emphasis was placed on identifying if and when governmental responses proceeded with a differentiated course of action, instead of the pre-set crisis management plan/mechanisms, whilst identifying the impact on each target country.

T4.2 conducts research on governmental responses by designing and carrying out primary empirical research on specified dimensions of governmental responses. Inputs have included indicators utilized in WP2, project-level research questions established in WP3, and baseline descriptive analyses per target country conducted in T4.1. Empirical research methods utilized in T4.2 have included qualitative expert interviews conducted with policymakers and/or policy experts ($N \geq 5$ per case study), reported in D4.3, and resident interviews (for more detail, see D3.6). The questions of this update in the methodology (D4.6) will similarly cover top-level factors identified in all WP4 tasks as well as specific topics of partner interest specified in T4.3, as relevant per case study, particularly during the period of early February 2022 until late May 2023.

Subsequently, these research activities will lead to the update of T4.3 *Assess and critique governmental responses on key dimensions of impact*, which is D4.7. This task will conduct in-depth analysis of specific dimensions of governmental responses and impacts in the project target countries, as guided by urgency in the target countries and partner research agendas.

2.1 Overview of the desktop and empirical research in WP4

As Table 2 outlines, the methodology utilised to address the WP4 research questions is a **qualitative approach**. More in particular, the WP4 research mainly focuses on exploring the more complex responses, and lessons learned related to the COVID-19 impact with input from governmental actors,

³ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, p12.

⁴ As it is elaborated further in D3.6 *Multi-site research design and methodological framework (update)*, a syndemic approach "Specifically, a syndemic approach examines why certain diseases cluster (i.e., multiple diseases affecting individuals and groups); the pathways through which they interact biologically in individuals and within populations, and thereby multiply their overall disease burden, and the ways in which social environments, especially conditions of social inequality and injustice, contribute to disease clustering and interaction as well as to vulnerability." (Singer, Bulled & Ostrach, 2017: p941).

public authorities, and policymakers as specific target populations. It aims to identify the reasons why specific decisions have been made, specific responses have been assessed as well as specific measures have been imposed, trying in that way to produce generalised knowledge for addressing similar situations, utilising semi-structured interviews with experts from the field as main research method.

Table 1. Example of Sociodemographic criteria for WP4 sampling population⁵.

Criteria	Minimum sample
Representative of a governmental authority/ministry etc. established before the COVID-19 pandemic	N≥1
Representative of a governmental authority/ministry etc particularly established to address the COVID-19 pandemic	N≥1
Self-identifies as woman	N≥2
Work is directly related to, and/or works directly with, vulnerable groups	N≥1

In the following subsections, the main empirical research methods that are applied in the empirical research of WP4 will be outlined. For all of them, researchers utilise the following research questions (see below), and they are provided with a protocol (for interviews) including specific guidelines, as well as an important material to conduct the interviews (e.g., informed consent and information sheets etc.). All the above-mentioned materials are provided in English⁶.

The empirical research in WP4 consisted of two main activities: expert interviews with governmental actors, public authorities, and policymakers as specified in Table 1 above, and interviews with residents, focusing on a specific vulnerable group: women with low socio-economic status (SES). While the expert interviews are work package-specific, the resident interviews with low SES women are shared between WP4-7 empirical research (for further information, see *D3.6 Multi-site research design and methodological framework - update M27*). To provide guidance to all research partners, WP4-7 leaders have formed a shared Fieldwork manual including all WP-specific sections (sampling, recruitment, topic guides) as well as standardized information and consent sheet, along with a standardized 'findings template' for each WP in which research partners can report their findings in English.

The research activities are guided by the following research questions, which serve as a safeguard for the studies to be as representative as possible. **The research questions that are examined in D4.6 and analyzed in D4.7 are presented below:**

1. What are the main milestones of the governmental responses adopted in each country during the different pandemic phases?
2. In what ways have governmental measures been implemented and adapted across communities/populations, and have they been received?
3. In what ways have governmental responses addressed specific vulnerabilities and inequalities across diverse communities/populations?
4. What was the experience of vulnerable groups in relation to governmental response?

⁵ These criteria overlap with each other, as e.g., one participant could identify as female and be a representative of governmental authority/ministry etc. established before the COVID-19 pandemic.

⁶ Wherever it is required, translations will be also be provided with the assistance of the consortium partners.

The following table provides an overview of the expert interviews conducted by the research partners in each of the research sites. As mentioned above, empirical research is ongoing until May 2023, so a complete set of expert and resident interviews can be reported in D4.7.

Table 2. Overview of WP4 expert interviews⁷.

Partner	Research site	Number of interviews
SYNYO	Austria	4 completed interviews – 1 interview pending
UANTWERPEN	Belgium	5 completed interviews
KEMEA	Greece	5 completed interviews
SAPIENZA, UCSC	Italy	4 completed interviews – 1 interview pending
FS	Portugal	5 completed interviews
SNCRR	Romania	4 completed interviews – 1 interview pending
URJC, SAMUR	Spain	5 completed interviews
UGOT	Sweden	5 completed interviews
TRI, MDI	England	3 completed interviews – 2 interviews pending
SU	Wales	2 completed interviews – 3 interviews pending
SINUS	Germany	5 interviews Pending ⁸

As can be seen in the table, some partners have experienced difficulties in completing all expert interviews in the first iteration of the research. In case partners could not submit their contribution for the initial empirical research (D4.3), the pending interviews, once completed and analysed, will be incorporated in the update of this task, deliverable 4.7. This document reports on the analysis of the previous data acquired in D4.2 and D4.3, as well as an in-depth examination of the research questions phrased in D4.6 for the aforementioned target countries.

The present report proceeds with recommending a feasible measure to mitigate the risk of data insufficiency, particularly in case project partners experience a significant degree of research data inadequacy and continue to be challenged by reachability and accessibility issues with the potential expert interviewees. Partners are strongly encouraged to utilise official, highly relevant documentation and content indicating decision and policy making processes that have been adopted by the highest governmental structure. The aforementioned documentation should be effective at a national, regional and local scope, as an integral part of the governmental responses and measures. This alternative course of action is provided as a risk mitigation measure to safeguard the contribution of partners, which drastically raises the rate of successfully completing the research indicated in D4.6,

⁷ Please refer to D4.3 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment, pp. 11 – 14.

⁸ SINUS has reported unprecedented difficulties in recruiting experts for the WP4 interviews. Several alternatives have been discussed between the WP leader, the coordinator, and SINUS, and are presented in the ANNEX.

while ensuring the inclusion of all target countries within D4.7 despite potential research related data risks.

3 Methodological reflections

The main methodological approach for the previous research activities within WP4 was desktop research and qualitative research methods with an emphasis in structured interviews of decision and policy makers, as well as resident interviews (for more detail, see D3.6).

Partners have utilized all ethical means and methods in the recruitment phase of research activities in WP4, particularly recruiting decision and policy makers. The aforementioned target group has been approached via formal invitations and utilizing pre-established communication networks between consortium members and relevant stakeholders.

The main challenge that has been identified in the empirical research of WP4 activities, particularly for conducting interviews with decision and policy makers, were issues of accessibility and availability, especially during periods in which the COVID-19 infection rate was significantly intensified, due to potential interviewee responsibilities and workload.

In order to mitigate these difficulties, partners sought alternative but equally important potential interviewees that have a direct affiliation with pandemic policy and decision-making processes within the target countries. In addition, partners have offered to conduct the interviews with the assistance of digital meeting platforms besides on-site interviews, based on interviewee availability.

No ethical issues occurred during WP4 research activities, whereas all potential ethical considerations were taken into account before the field research.

Empirical research presented in deliverables across WP4-7 is analysed according to the themes of the WPs and the research teams' expertise. Additionally, there is a common framework for analysis spanning for all WPs and domains. This will enable the COVINFORM project to discuss findings across WPs.

Finally, as mentioned above, one partner in particular has faced difficulties in recruiting experts for interviews. As such, the WP leader has designed a strategy to mitigate the risk of potential data acquisition challenges. This is presented in the ANNEX.

4 Conclusions

The main lessons learned of the research design for the activities within WP4 is that partners can and are advised to examine governmental responses and their impacts, initially from a holistic perspective with a broader scope at an EU, national, regional and local level. It is recommended, that partners should narrow down the research scope to more targeted research questions in accordance with the latest developments and research gaps, as research progresses, in order to avoid unnecessary repetition. The main difficulties of designing and carrying out research was the unavoidable highly dynamic and ever-changing landscape of policy and decision making upon facing an unprecedented pandemic, such as COVID-19, and relevant recruitment challenges, due to the fact that decision and policy makers at a national level have severely limited availability to participate in the empirical research (interviews).

KEMEA (WP Leader) in collaboration with TRI (Task Leader) will integrate the reports of D4.7 at the end of May, 2023 (M31). Subsequently, KEMEA will utilize valuable data that stem from the aforementioned report and initiate D4.8: Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33 [33], with a deadline July 2023.

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WP4 Deliverables

Available for download at <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/technical-reports/>

- D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses.
- D4.2 Research design: Governmental responses.
- D4.3 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment.
- D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts.
- D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22.

ANNEX. Risk mitigation strategy

The research activity framework D4.6 establishes for the update of the empirical research in WP4 takes into consideration the assessment of governmental responses which require the acquisition and utilization of relevant empirical data through qualitative research between early February 2022 and late May 2023. To mitigate the risk of potential data acquisition challenges, upon consortium member discretion, partners have the option to conduct additional qualitative, quantitative and/or desktop research to supplement their contribution to the research activities related to D4.7. This option is available and is provided as a feasible option for partners, particularly if challenged by relevant data inadequacy. Partner contribution is estimated to be in a concise format, a brief 1-2-page report summary on the main inputs from each country.

Language

The language that will be included in the research will be mainly English. However, due to the specific particularities of the research (governmental responses usually are issued in the national/regional language and there is not an English translation), all the entries will be accepted on the premise that the partners will provide a comprehensive and detailed English description of the main points of each entry and its relevance to the research.

Timeframe

The entries should cover the period from early February 2022 until late May 2023 with clear distinction among the relevant waves of the pandemic and vaccination initiatives in each country for comparison purposes among governmental structure/decisions/responses and vaccination campaign.

Exclusion criteria

Entries with no focus on the subject of research, with no available details abstract in English, with no available free text or not compliant with GDPR and/or research ethics standards, e.g. private social media profiles, data gathered in an unethical way will be excluded.

Timeline for the research and next steps

Consortium partners will be asked to provide their research entries until **10.04.2023**, focusing on **their respective countries**. The final research findings can be uploaded on the respective google drive folder, can be sent to **KEMEA (WP Leader)** and the respective colleagues of **Trilateral (Task Leader)**.

KEMEA (WP Leader) in collaboration with Trilateral (Task Leader) will be responsible for the collection, the review and the systematic report of the empirical research, which will be reported to D4.7 in April, 2023 (M30) and submitted in May, 2023 (M31).

All the participants are kindly requested to conduct empirical research on their respective countries. Due to the fact that some consortium partners come from the same countries, they can collaborate in this report jointly, until **10.04.2023**, and send it to **KEMEA (WP Leader)** and **Trilateral (Task Leader)**.